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The Collaborative Austrian Youth Language Dictionary

Capturing current trends in a variety of digital formats and media has been widely practiced across disciplines in recent years. Across the generations, but particularly with the younger generations, digital media have become a vital means of communication, as well as a reliable support for teaching and learning.

Here we present a recent corpus of youth language collected together with a group of around twenty youths in a workshop held in Austria at *KinderUniSteyr* (“Wie sich die Sprache verändert”, 2016) and elaborate on how digital access and connectivity of such a corpus is enabled with the help of Digital Humanities (DH) tools such as the Viennese Lexicographic Editor (VLE) (c.f. Budin, Moerth & Durco, 2013; Moerth, Procházka & Dallaji, 2014). Locating youth language in a DH context provides so far largely unexploited ways of accessing, editing and archiving a corpus of rapidly evolving terms, which could prove fruitful for scholars and (non-)scientists alike.

The general aim of the workshop was to experience interaction between science and scientists, and the local youth, elaborating on Austrian youth culture. The authors started with an investigation on linguistic features, how young people name the world and what cultural experiences represented in linguistic concepts are most relevant for dialectal words or for the stimulation of new word creations. The collected words were then digitized employing the VLE. This DH tool was selected for processing, as it provides a number of useful functions to automate editing procedures, allows to process standard-based lexicographic and terminological data, and thus constitutes our basis for collaborative editing, future enlargement and wide-ranging accessibility of these data.

This poster gives an overview of this joint effort: *The Collaborative Austrian Youth Language Dictionary*, employing the Viennese Lexicographic Editor (VLE), and also intends to offer a first conceptual approach towards the open pilot project “Austrian Youth Culture: Creative Exploratory Knowledge Interaction”.

Bibliography:

Budin, G., Moerth, K., Durco, M. (2013) *European Lexicography Infrastructure Components*. Proceedings of eLex2013, Tallin, Estonia.

Moerth, K., Procházka, S., & Dallaji, I. (2014) *Laying the Foundations for a Diachronic Dictionary of Tunis Arabic: a First Glance at an Evolving New Language Resource*. Proceedings of XVI EURALEX 2014, Bolzano, Italy.

Viennese Lexicographic Editor (VLE)
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“Wie sich die Sprache verändert.” (2016). Workshop at KinderUniSteyr 28.09.2016.
<http://kinderuni-oe.at/index.php/kinderuni-steyr-programm/item/2424-wie-sich-die-sprache-veraendert--317731> [last accessed 20.11.2016]